

Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS) with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word "BPRS" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around BPRS based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer Behavior; (4) Financing products; (5) Savings products; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding BPRS, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS); Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

The first Sharia bank in Indonesia, Bank Muamalat, was founded on November 1 1991. Before Law Number 7 of 1992 was passed, this bank was able to exist by carrying out sharia-compliant activities. Bank Muamalat Indonesia's success in its business is due to the use of sharia principles. Then, various other sharia financial institutions emerged in Indonesia, including Bank Mandiri Syariah (BSM), Bank BNI Syariah, Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS), and others. One of the sharia financial institutions in Indonesia is the Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS). The existence of BPRS in Indonesia is supported by the demands of Islamic muamalah and the economy, as shown in various publications regarding finance, monetary and banking. BPRS adheres to sharia law by using agreements based on Islamic law between banks and other parties to save money and finance business activities or other activities deemed to be in accordance with sharia, including financing based on the principle of profit sharing (Mudharabah), financing based on the principle of capital participation (Musyarakah), or financing based on the principle of buying and selling goods for profit (Murabahah).

Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS) have a role in improving economic welfare, especially for micro, small and medium economic communities in rural areas which are the main targets. Apart from that, BPRS also acts as a financial intermediary and resource for MSME business actors. The development of

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is one of the main drivers of Indonesia's economic growth in the real sector. The increase in the amount of financing provided by BPRS every year shows the public's trust in BPRS in financing MSMEs. This is also reflected in the growth in the number of MSMEs in Indonesia that can access financing products offered by BPRS.

BPRS are not advised to open current account savings products, participate in payment traffic, or carry out foreign exchange activities, except for foreign currency conversions. The business activities of BPRS and other sharia banks must follow sharia principles determined by the DSN-MUI Fatwa. Bank Indonesia monitors BPRS compliance with sharia principles through the Sharia Banking Committee (KPS). In addition, BPRS and other Islamic banks must have a Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) whose task is to provide advice to the board of directors and monitor bank activities so that they comply with sharia principles.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS) use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), whether frequently or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the research gaps in this topic.

Literature Review

Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS) is one of the sharia banks in Indonesia which is chosen by many people to develop businesses, especially micro, small and medium businesses. BPRS provides financial assistance to small and medium communities. According to Law of the Republic of Indonesia no. 21 Article 1 Paragraph 6 of 2008, BPRS is considered a sharia bank. However, SRB does not offer payment processing services. The financing products offered by BPRS are sharia banking products.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such

as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS). The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS) " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis techniques by mapping research topics around Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS) based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Sharia Rural Financing Banks (BPRS)

Search results on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS) from 2000 to 2022 show that the number of publications varies every year, especially in the last 5 years. In 2021, there were the most publications related to Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), namely 122 articles. This shows that the average scientific publication is around 3 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS)

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2000	1	2011	1	2017	55
2002	1	2012	11	2018	62
2003	1	2013	16	2019	70
2008	2	2014	17	2020	81
2009	3	2015	24	2021	122
2010	1	2016	28	2022	18
Total 514					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2019.

Table 2 shows data on affiliations/institutions with the largest number of published research articles regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS). The Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics is an affiliate/journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), with a total of 17 articles.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing journals regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS)

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics	17
MONETARY	11
IQTISHADIA: Journal of Sharia Economics & Banking, BAABU AL-ILMI Journal: Sharia Economics and Banking, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, NISBAH: JOURNAL OF SHARIA BANKING	9
AL-INFAQ	8
Sharia Banking Student Scientific Journal (JIMPA)	7
Journal of Finance and Accounting Research	6
ACCURATE UNIBBA FE Scientific Accounting Journal, Al-Masraf: Journal of Financial and Banking Institutions, EQUILIBRIUM, IQTISHADIA, Journal of Islamic Economics & Finance, Scientific Journal of Accounting Economics Students,	5
Al-bank: Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance, Al-Iqtishad: Journal of Sharia Economics, AL-MUZARA'AH, Indonesian Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, JESI (Indonesian Sharia Economic Journal), Journal of Justisia Ekonomika: Masters in Sharia Economic Law, MAXIMUM, Mabny: Journal of Sharia Management and Business, MASLAHAH (Journal of Islamic Law and Sharia Banking), SAHID BANKING JOURNAL,	4
Akbis: Accounting and Business Research Media, Accountability, Al-Intaj: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Ar-Ribhu: Journal of Sharia Management and Finance, Banque Syar'i: Scientific Journal of Sharia Banking, Expansion: Journal of Economics, Finance, Banking and Accounting, EKSYAR: Journal of Sharia Economics & Islamic Business, ETIKONOMI, Islamic Banking: Journal of Sharia Banking Thought and Development,	3

Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Finance, Journal of Accounting and Tax, Al-Hakim Journal: Student Scientific Journal, Sharia Studies, Law and Philanthropy, Economic Appreciation Journal, ASET (Research Accounting) Journal, JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND DEVELOPMENT POLICY, FEB Student Scientific Journal, Management and Professional Journal, MALIA: Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance

Ad-Deenar: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Adzkiya: Journal of Sharia Law and Economics, AL AMWAL (SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW), AL-FALAH: Journal of Islamic Economics, AT-TAWASSUTH: Journal of Islamic Economics, Bulletin of Monetary Economics and Banking, Dinar: Journal of Sharia Economics Study Program, DIRHAM Journal of Islamic Economics, Ekonomika Sharia: Journal of Sharia Economic Thought and Development, SHARIA ECONOMICS: Journal of Economic Studies, El-Ecosy: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, El-Iqtishod: Journal of Sharia Economics, El-Mal: Journal of Islamic Economics & Business Studies, Falah: Journal of Sharia Economics, FINANSIA: Journal of Sharia Accounting and Banking, HUMAN FALAH: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business Studies, Ihtiyath: Journal of Sharia Financial Management, International Journal of Community Service Learning, IQTISHADIA, IQTISHADUNA, Islamadina: Journal of Islamic Thought, Islamic Economics Journal, ISTIKHLAF: Journal of Sharia Economics, Banking and Management, JABE (Journal of Applied Business and Economics), JIES: Journal of Islamic Economics Studies, Journal of Sharia Banking, Journal of Business Administration, Journal of Accounting, ACCOUNTING AND INVESTMENT JOURNAL, ACCOUNTING, ECONOMICS and BUSINESS MANAGEMENT JOURNAL, Asas Journal, Dimamu Journal, Economic Journal, Dharma Andalas Economics and Business Journal, SHARIA ECONOMICS AND BANKING JOURNAL, Sharia Economics, Accounting and Banking Journal (JESKaPe), MEA Scientific Journal (Management, Economics & Accounting), Journal of Accounting and Sharia Business (AKSY), Journal of Economic and Development Studies, DIVERSIFICATION Management Journal, Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Mitra Management Journal, Indonesian Journal of Management Science and Business, Kasaba, LABATILA: Journal of Islamic Economics, Liquidity: Journal of Accounting and Management Research, MENARA ECONOMY, MUAMALAH, Performance, PERFORMANCE: Journal of Business & Accounting, Perisai: Islamic Banking and Finance Journal, Tazkia Islamic Finance and Business Review, Tadabbur: Journal Islamic Civilization, SOCIETY.

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Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2019.

Table 3 shows that the most productive researchers are Mochamad Indrajit Roy and Trimulato with 3 articles each. Meanwhile, other authors only wrote 1 scientific journal related to Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS).

Table 3. Research productivity regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS)

Researcher	Number of Publications
Mochamad Indrajit Roy; Trimulato	3
Zainal Abidin; Abdul Nasser Hasibuan; Hasyim Hasnil; Uus Ahmad Husaeni; Early Ridho Kismawadi; Safitri A, Laila N; Ningsih W, Badina T, Rosiana R; Anton Sudrajat; Trimulato; Muhammad Yunus;	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2019.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS)

The research results are based on the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) which is exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Network visualization of research development maps regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS)

Source: Data processed using VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

The results of the visual analysis of the network co-word map of research developments regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS) which are divided into 6 clusters and 384 topics, as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 124 topics, namely: agreement, activity, agreement, application, approach, aspect, attention, author, bank, banking, benefits, BPRS Al Falah Banyuasin, BPRS Amanah Ummah, business, capacity, capital, case, case study, collateral,

community, condition, contract, covid, credit, customer, data analysis, data analysis technique, data collection technique, data source, debtor, default, deposit, development, difference, distribution, documentation, dps, etc. mui, etc. mui fatwa, dsn mui ii, economy, effort, existence, factor, fatwa, feasibility, field, field research, financial institution, financing product, form, fund, growth, human resource, impact, implementation, interest, interview, investment, islamic banking, Islamic financial institute, loan, management, market share, medium enterprise, month, mudharabah, mudharabah financing, muarabahah financing, need, object, observation, operation, pandemic, paper, part, percent, perception, person, practice, primary data, principle, problem, procedure, process, product, provision, psak, public, qualitative approach, qualitative method, qualitative research, research method, research result, responsibility, risk management, role, saving, secondary data, settlement, sharia, sharia financial institution, sharia principle, sharia supervisory board, unpublished thesis, small, society, source, srb, stage, strategy, case study, study show, supervision, surabaya, system, technique, term, time, type, use, way, year.

- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 86 topics, namely: ability, amount, analysis, analysis technique, average value, barokah saving, BPRS Bhakti Sumekar, coefficient, company, competence, competition, compliance, customer decision, customer loyalty, customer, satisfaction, data collection, decision, determination, ease, education, effect, effectiveness, employee, employee performance, f test, financial statement, gili genting pratama branch office, hypothesis, indicator, influence, information, islamic, work ethic, job satisfaction, keyword, level, Library Research, loyalty, Madura, marketing, mean, money, multiple linear regression, net income, number, order, part, percentage, performance, population, price, promotion, PT BPRS Wangar Hikmahnugaraha, PT BPRS Hik Parahyangan Bandug, PT BPRS jabal nur, quality, quantitative approach, quantitative method, quantitative research, questionnaire, real sector, reason, relationship, reliability, report, research, researcher, respondent, sample, sampling technique, satisfaction, service, service quality, sharia person, significance level, significant effect, significant influence, spss, study, t test, test, test result, training, value, variable, work, work discipline.
- Cluster 3. The dark blue color consists of 62 topics, namely: analysis, data analysis, bank Indonesia, Islamic Rural Banks, sharia bank, based on, bopo, bpr, bprs, bprs amanah insan cita, bus, contribution, in, and, and documentation, from, data, data envelopment analysis, DEA, with, descriptive, efficiency, factors, factors, GCG, good corporate governance, this, the results of this research show, the results of the research show, West Java, keywords, institutions, methods, msmes, murabahah, musyarakah, however, ojk, in Islamic Rural Bankss, pbi, financing, murabahah financing, this research, this research aims, this research uses, period, one, in, case studies in, sharia, years, against, The aim of this research is to test UMKM for UUS variables, interviews, West Java.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 44 topics, namely: assets, asset quality, board, sharia bpr, capital adequacyratio, car, central java, deposit ratio, description, director, dpk, earnings, equity, fdr, financial performance, financial ratio, financial report, financing, independent

variable, Islamic bank, Islamic rural bank, liquidity, manager, mudharabah deposit, multiple linear regression analysis, non-performing financing, npf, starting financing, period, portion, positive effect, profit, profit sharing, profitability, purposive sampling, ratio, return, roa, roe, rural bank, square, third party fund, total assets.

- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 25 topics, namely: abstract, addition, bi rate, December, determinant, external factors, finance, financial services authority, http, Indonesia, Indonesian period, inflation, internal factors, Jakarta, January, journal, model, org, financial services authority, influence, risk, sharia rural bank, sharia banking statistics, wwwojk, yogyakarta.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 7 topics, namely: bank financing, income, increase, Islamic people, Islamic person, musyarakah financing, operational income.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Sharia Rural Financing Banks (BPRS)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 20 topics related to BPRS financial performance, namely:

First, the influence of Third Party Funds/TPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, Non-Performing Financing /NPF on asset growth. The influence of TPF, FDR, and NPF on asset growth can greatly influence the financial health of BPRS. If DPK increases and is used efficiently for financing (FDR is maintained at a healthy level), and NPF remains low, then BPRS asset growth tends to be positive. However, if TPF decreases, FDR is not maintained, and NPF increases, this could result in slow or even declining asset growth due to high credit risk and limited availability of funds.

Second, Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR is viewed from Shariah Enterprise Theory. Shariah Enterprise Theory is an approach that integrates Islamic sharia principles into business practices and company operations. CSR in this context refers to a company's social responsibility in achieving its business goals in line with sharia principles, such as justice, balance and sharing with society. CSR in BPRS must be based on Islamic values, including support for social, environmental and general welfare activities that are in accordance with religious teachings.

Third, managing regional assets through capital ownership. Management of regional assets through capital ownership refers to the BPRS strategy of investing or owning shares in businesses related to the region where the BPRS operates. Through this capital ownership, BPRS can have an active role in regional development, support local economic growth, and strengthen BPRS involvement in the surrounding social and economic environment.

Fourth, the influence of Third Party Funds/TPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, Non-Performing Financing /NPF on total assets. DPK, FDR, and NPF also influence the total assets of BPRS. Healthy DPK and FDR growth as well as low NPF levels are likely to have a positive impact on increasing total BPRS assets. On the other hand, an unhealthy condition of these indicators can hinder the growth of total assets.

Fifth, the influence of BPRS on the development of MSMEs and agribusiness. BPRS has an important role in developing the MSME (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) and agribusiness sectors. Through sharia principles, BPRS can provide financing in accordance with Islamic principles to MSMEs

and the agribusiness sector, as well as provide support and training to increase the business capacity and abilities of business actors in these sectors.

Sixth, the effect of profitability on liquidity. Profitability refers to the ability of a BPRS to generate profits from its operations. Liquidity, on the other hand, measures the availability of cash and liquid assets to meet short-term obligations. The influence of profitability on liquidity can be interconnected. If an SRB focuses heavily on achieving a high level of profitability, it may increase liquidity risk because less cash is available to meet short-term needs. On the other hand, if an SRB focuses too much on liquidity and holds too many funds in low liquidity forms, its profitability may be affected because the potential profits from more profitable investments are not maximized.

Seventh, the influence of Gross Domestic Product/GDP, inflation, Profit Sharing Payment Intensity /MMR, Murabahah margin, working capital, investment, Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO to Non Performing Financing / NPF.

Eighth, the influence of Non-Performing Financing /NPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Operational Efficiency Ratio /OER, Good Corporate Governance /GCG, type of customer, frequency of financing disbursement, liquidity management, Operational Costs on Operational Income/ BOPO, financing (Murabahah, Musyarakah, Mudharabah, Qardh, Ijarah, Istishna', agricultural sector, consumer, working capital), transaction costs, interest rates, Covid-19, receivables turnover, intellectual capital, problematic financing, liquidity, company size, teacher certification financing products, human resource accounting, income sharing from Mudharabah deposits, Tauhid String Relations/ TSR, fixed asset turnover, Earning Asset Quality, Fee-Based Income on financial performance/profitability/ROA/ROE.

Ninth, the influence of capital, asset quality, efficiency on returns. (1) Sufficient capital will help banks face possible risks, such as credit risk, liquidity risk and market risk. The higher the capital owned by a BPRS, the greater its ability to bear risks, so that it can provide confidence to customers and stakeholders that the bank is stable and reliable. Capital also plays a role in determining the ability of BPRS to finance and expand its business reach. (2) Asset quality refers to how good the quality of the financing or investment portfolio owned by the BPRS is. Good quality assets are assets that have low credit risk, that is, debtors or borrowers tend to pay back their obligations on schedule. If asset quality is poor, the BPRS will face high credit risks, such as the possibility of bad credit or debtor default. Therefore, banks must have good credit risk management procedures and carry out regular monitoring of the quality of their assets. (3) Efficiency refers to the ability of BPRS to manage its resources as well as possible to achieve optimal results. Efficiency can be measured from the ratio of operational costs to operating income. The lower this ratio, the more efficient the BPRS is in managing its operational costs. Good operational efficiency can increase the ability of BPRS to generate higher profits, while providing benefits to customers in the form of more competitive products and services.

Tenth, the influence of Musyarakah financing, Murabahah financing, profit sharing ratio, inflation, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, money supply, promotional costs, number of accounts, services, equivalent rate, profitability, number of offices, and BI rate on Third Party Funds/DPK.

Eleventh, financial performance through the Maqashid Shariah Index /MSI, Two Stage Data Envelopment Analysis /DEA, Shariah Conformity and Profitability /SCnP, Risk Based Bank Rating, SFA, Balanced Scorecard and Direct Error Correlation Model approaches.

Twelfth, commercial and social integration of Islamic finance. The commercial and social integration of Islamic finance refers to a sharia bank's approach to running a business that combines sharia economic principles with social responsibility. This means that this bank is not only profit-oriented, but also strives to contribute to social welfare and community economic development.

Thirteenth, the influence of the amount of wadiah savings and investment funds is not tied to Murabahah receivables. The influence of the amount of wadiah savings and untied investment funds on Murabahah receivables means that wadiah savings and investment funds are not used directly for Murabahah model financing. The Murabahah financing model is a sale and purchase transaction with a price markup which is the basis for financing in Islamic banks. So, wadiah savings and investment funds are more likely to be used for investment activities and liquidity management, rather than as a direct source of Murabahah financing.

Fourteenth, the total influence of Musyarakah financing, Murabahah financing, Non Performing Financing /NPF on income. The total influence of Musyarakah financing, Murabahah financing, and NPF on income reflects the quality of bank assets and its influence on bank income. The greater the amount of Musyarakah financing and Murabahah financing that is successfully paid by the customer, the higher the bank's income from profit sharing schemes and price markups. However, a high NPF level can reduce income because banks have to bear losses due to bad financing.

Fifteenth, the effect of investment in receivables on profitability. The effect of investment in receivables on profitability describes the extent to which a bank's receivables portfolio can generate profits for the bank. If the investment in receivables is successful, the bank will obtain income from margins or profit sharing which will increase its profitability.

Sixteenth, the influence of the subsidized sharia micro housing program on health level performance. The influence of the subsidized sharia micro housing program on health level performance reflects how the implementation of the program contributes to the bank's financial performance and health. This program can affect bank assets, financing quality, income, and others, so that it can have an impact on the bank's overall performance.

Seventeenth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Operational Costs on Operational Income / BOPO, Return On Assets / ROA, Net Interest Margin / NIM, Musyarakah and Murabahah financing on Financing to Deposit Ratio / FDR.

Eighteenth, the influence of total assets, capital, financing, Mudharabah deposits, operational income, Qardh receivables, cash turnover, wadiah savings, Murabahah receivables, Third Party Funds/TPF, estimated amount, loan money on net profit.

Nineteenth, the influence of the audit committee, implementation of PSAK (101, 105) and the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS on the quality of financial reports. (1) The audit committee is an independent body responsible for supervising and evaluating the accounting process, financial reporting and internal control systems at BPRS. The presence of an audit committee is very important to ensure transparency, accuracy and reliability of bank financial

reports. With the existence of an audit committee, it is hoped that there will be an effective internal mechanism to detect and prevent errors or fraud in financial processes. (2) PSAK 101 regulates Disclosures in Financial Reports, while PSAK 105 regulates Mudharabah and Musyarakah Accounting. The implementation of this PSAK will ensure that BPRS follows generally accepted accounting standards, so that bank financial reports are consistent, standardized and easy to compare with other banks. (3) The Sharia Supervisory Board is the institution responsible for ensuring that all activities and transactions at the BPRS comply with Islamic sharia principles. DPS plays an important role in ensuring BPRS compliance with sharia principles, and also ensuring that the financial reports produced are free from transactions that are not in accordance with Islamic values.

Twentieth, the influence of Wadiah savings, Murabahah financing, and Mudharabah financing on operating revenues. (1) The influence of Wadiah's savings on BPRS operating revenue lies in the funds collected from Wadiah's savings which can be used to carry out financing and other investments, so that they can contribute to the bank's operational income. (2) The effect of Murabahah financing on the operating revenue of BPRS is to gain profits from the difference in purchase price and selling price of the goods financed. This profit will become a source of operational income for BPRS. (3) The influence of Mudharabah financing on BPRS operating revenue is from the distribution of profits obtained from businesses financed jointly with customers. As capital owner, BPRS will share in the profits of the business.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Performance of Sharia Rural Bank (BPRS) Employees

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 46 topics related to the performance of BPRS employees, namely: (1) Employee benefits; (2) Interpersonal communication; (3) Motivation; (4) Organizational culture; (5) Work experience; (6) Education level; (7) Work discipline; (8) Leadership; (9) Job training; (10) Management; (11) Self-efficacy; (12) HR Competency; (13) Compensation; (14) Job placement; (15) Professionalism; (16) Job characteristics; (17) Job satisfaction; (18) Psychological capital; (19) Manager's understanding; (20) Salary; (21) Office layout; (22) Planning; (23) Forecasting; (24) Functional training; (25) Career coaching; (26) Employee placement; (27) Organizational commitment; (28) Celestial management for HR; (29) Role of Commissioners and Sharia Supervisory Board; (30) Providing incentives and bonuses; (31) Intellectual ability; (32) Work ethic; (33) Transformational leadership; (34) Islamic economic values; (35) Islamic governance; (36) Diversity; (37) Personality; (38) Work engagement; (39) Benefits; (40) Job stress; (41) Archives management; (42) Workplace Spirituality; (43) Work environment; (44) Standard Operating Procedures; (45) Supervision; (46) Financing for employees.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Customer Behavior of Sharia Rural Financing Banks (BPRS))

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 60 topics related to BPRS customer behavior, namely: (1) Personal selling; (2) Selling price; (3) Product quality; (4) Service quality; (5) Margin cut/ muqashah ar-ribh; (6) Relationship marketing; (7) Islamic marketing; (8) Islamic business ethics; (9) Religiosity; (10) Demographics; (11) Social comfort; (12) Technology; (13) Information integration; (14) Process of providing financing;

(15) Preference; (16) Trust; (17) Contract; (18) Football pick-up service; (19) Social capital; (20) Local wisdom; (21) Economic factors; (22) Marketing funding officer; (23) Differentiation; (24) Positioning; (25) Charter dimensions; (26) Marketing mix; (27) After-sales service for motorbike products; (28) Frontliners competency; (29) Sharia financial literacy; (30) Savings pick-up and drop-off; (31) Advertising/promotion; (32) Margin level; (33) Equivalent rate of profit sharing; (34) deposit interest rates; (35) Number of offices; (36) Handling complaints; (37) Direct service; (38) Relationship marketing; (39) Demographics/location; (40) Brand Image; (41) Perceived benefits; (42) Logistic regression; (43) Covid-19 pandemic; (44) Information technology; (45) Giving gifts; (46) Online services; (47) Timeliness of service; (48) Knowledge; (49) Profit margin; (50) Company image; (51) Management commitment; (52) Loan sharks; (53) Rational motivation; (54) Income level; (55) Customer Service; (56) Sharia Compliance; (57) World of Mouth; (58) Profit sharing from deposits; (59) Effective communication; (60) Brand Equity.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Financing Products at Sharia Rural Banks (BPRS))

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 30 topics related to financing products at BPRS, namely:

First, a support system for making MSME financing decisions. This system uses various data and information from prospective customers, such as financial reports, credit history, business profiles, etc., to assist in the decision-making process as to whether financing can be approved or not. This system also helps in determining the amount of financing that can be provided as well as the financing conditions that must be met by prospective customers.

Second, the principles for implementing financing (shariah, prudence, 5C, customer recognition, fairness). (1) Sharia, meaning that all financing products and services offered must comply with Islamic sharia principles. This means that transactions must be free from usury (interest), maysir (gambling), gharar (obscurity), and other things that are forbidden in Islam. (2) The precautionary principle requires banks to carefully evaluate risks before providing financing to prospective customers. This process involves analyzing business feasibility, potential customers' capabilities, and potential risks that may occur. (3) The 5C principle is an abbreviation of Character, Capacity, Capital, Collateral and Conditions which are used to assess prospective customers' credit. The bank will assess the character of the prospective customer, capacity to repay the financing, capital owned, type of guarantee that can be provided, and economic and market conditions in the business sector concerned. (4) Customer Introduction, this principle emphasizes the importance of banks getting to know their potential customers well. The aim is for banks to understand the character, needs and potential of customers so that they can provide appropriate financing and provide benefits for both parties. (5) The principle of justice means that banks must provide financing with terms and conditions that are fair and do not harm either party.

Third, the application of Murabahah financing, Murabahah bil Wakalah, Rahn for gold pawning, gold-backed Musyarakah, house renovation, and Ijarah.

Fourth, fiduciary guarantee for Murabahah financing. Fiduciary guarantee in Murabahah financing is a form of guarantee for financing provided by BPRS to customers. In this case, the customer provides collateral for certain goods or assets as collateral for the financing received. The collateralized assets will belong to the bank on a fiduciary basis (trust) until the customer pays off

all financing obligations. If the customer cannot repay the financing according to the agreement, the bank has the right to sell the assets to pay off the customer's debt.

Fifth, the influence of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Third Party Funds/DPK, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, Return On Assets /ROA, Non Performing Financing /NPF, company size, efficiency, inflation, small business classification, internal audit, BI rate, profit sharing ratio, non-current financing, own capital, written off productive assets, determination of margin on financing.

Sixth, CAMEL ratio analysis. The acronym CAMEL itself represents the five aspects analyzed, namely: (1) Capital: Evaluation of the level of bank capital and its adequacy to cover the risks faced. (2) Asset Quality: Evaluation of the quality of the bank's asset portfolio, especially in terms of credit risk or problematic financing. (3) Management: Assessment of management's effectiveness in managing risk, business strategy and compliance with regulations. (4) Earnings: Analysis of the bank's financial performance, including profitability and ability to generate income. (5) Liquidity: Assessment of the bank's ability to meet its financial obligations as they fall due.

Seventh, development of Natural Uncertainty Contract /NUC financing in the productive sector. In NUC, risk distribution is carried out fairly based on the capital contribution of each party. If the project makes a profit, the results are shared according to the agreement. However, if the project experiences a loss, the risk will also be shared according to the proportion of ownership. In this way, NUC encourages partnership and togetherness between banks and customers in supporting the productive sector.

Eighth, problem financing/bad credit with debtor information systems, POAC (planning, organizing, actuating, controlling), CART (Classification and Regression Trees), SWOT (Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats), and prudent principles of banking. (1) Debtor Information System: Information system that records and monitors customer data related to financing owned, including payment performance, obligations and credit history. This helps banks to monitor financing risks and identify potential financing problems. (2) POAC: Management concept which includes planning, organizing, implementing and controlling in financing management. With this approach, banks can plan and manage financing more efficiently and effectively. (3) CART: Data analysis method used to classify customers based on various factors and characteristics. In the context of financing, this method can help banks assess credit risk and identify customers with potential problems. (4) SWOT: SWOT analysis of the bank or its financing portfolio. SWOT analysis helps banks to recognize their position in the market, identify risks and opportunities, and formulate appropriate strategies. (5) Prudent Principle of Banking: The principle of applying prudence in risk management by banks. In the context of financing, banks need to maintain a reasonable level of risk in providing financing, as well as diversifying their portfolio to reduce concentration risk.

Ninth, implementation of financing for motor vehicle purchases and manufacturing. In financing motor vehicle purchases, the bank will buy the vehicle the customer wants, then sell it to the customer at a set price and a clear markup (profit). The customer will pay periodically according to the agreement. Meanwhile, in manufacturing financing, banks can provide financing for business capital, purchase of machinery and equipment, or production expansion for the manufacturing sector.

Tenth, financing risk management. Risks in financing include credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, market risk, and others. Sharia Rural Financing Banks must apply the principle of prudence in managing risks so that they remain stable and sustainable in providing financing to customers. Good risk management helps banks to reduce potential losses and ensure the availability of sufficient funds to fulfill obligations to customers.

Eleventh, determining the selling price and profit margin for Murabahah financing. To determine the selling price and profit margin for Murabahah financing, BPRS needs to consider several factors, including the purchase price of goods, operational costs, risks, market interest rates, and a reasonable profit margin in accordance with sharia principles. Banks must be transparent in setting prices and ensure that the profits obtained are halal and in accordance with sharia provisions.

Twelfth, Account Officer / AO strategy in achieving financing targets during the Covid-19 pandemic. In facing the pandemic situation, AO needs to adopt appropriate strategies to achieve financing targets, including: (1) Utilization of Technology: AO must rely on digital communication and marketing technology to reach potential customers. This may involve utilizing social media, email, or other online platforms. (2) Evaluation of Customer Needs: AO needs to identify business sectors or projects that still have the potential to develop during the pandemic and provide financing that is relevant to these customers' needs. (3) Adjustment of Financing Procedures: AO can adjust financing procedures to reduce the administrative burden for customers and speed up the approval process. (4) Providing Flexible Financing Solutions: AO must be able to provide financing solutions that are flexible and appropriate to customers' financial situations that may be affected by the pandemic. (5) Improve Service and Communication: AO must communicate actively with customers and provide better service to maintain customer trust.

Thirteenth, fines for problematic financing. To avoid problematic financing, BPRS must ensure careful credit evaluation before providing financing to customers. If there is a delay or non-compliance with payment, BPRS can impose a fine as part of the sanctions for the violation. However, in the context of sharia financing, fines must be regulated carefully and in accordance with sharia principles to avoid usury (interest). The fines imposed must be hortatory in nature, that is, as a warning or encouragement for customers to comply with their obligations, not as a source of income for the BPRS.

Fourteenth, self-certification letter (*asta de vita*) as a condition for financing. The Personal Information Letter is used by BPRS as initial data in the credit analysis process. The data contained in it will help BPRS to assess customers' suitability for obtaining financing. The truth and accuracy of the information provided by prospective customers in *Asta de Vita* is very important, because it will influence the subsequent process, including determining the amount of financing and the level of credit risk.

Fifteenth, the influence of the amount of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on the money supply. The influence of the amount of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on the money supply depends on the mechanism of fund flow in the economy. When BPRS provides this financing, money circulation will increase because the funds provided to customers are used for business activities or investments, which in turn will flow to various economic sectors. A significant and well-targeted amount of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing can make a positive contribution to economic growth and

increase business activity, thereby having an impact on increasing the amount of money circulating in society.

Sixteenth, evaluate financing using the Analytical Hierarchy Process /AHP, Break Even Point, and Early Warning System /AWS. (1) AHP is a decision-making method used to assist BPRS in evaluating and prioritizing financing alternatives based on various relevant criteria. In this process, criteria and alternatives are weighted to determine the most optimal choice. Examples of criteria that can be evaluated using AHP are credit risk, profit potential, and compliance with sharia principles. (2) BEP is the point at which total revenue equals total costs. In financing, BEP is used to determine the minimum amount of financing that must be approved to reach the break-even point or without profit or loss. BEP analysis helps BPRS to understand the level of financing that must be achieved so that its business remains sustainable. (3) AWS is a system used to detect early potential problems with financing, such as high credit risk or the possibility of bad credit. This system uses various indicators and parameters to provide warnings to BPRS so that they can take preventive action before financing experiences more serious problems.

Seventeenth, application of PAPSI and PSAK to multiservice financing products. The implementation of PAPSI and PSAK in multiservice financing products aims to ensure transparency and compliance with sharia principles as well as present accurate and reliable financial information for customers, shareholders and other related parties.

Eighteenth, the influence of debtor behavior and customer financial report information on providing financing. (1) Debtor behavior, such as compliance in paying installments on time, can have a significant effect on providing financing. Debtors who have a good credit history and are disciplined in paying installments will be considered more creditable and have a higher chance of getting financing with favorable terms and conditions. (2) Information on customer financial reports is used by BPRS to assess credit worthiness and credit risks related to providing financing. Financial reports that present customers' business performance, income level, cash flow and overall financial health will help BPRS make the right decisions in offering appropriate financing.

Nineteenth, the influence of financing on customer perceptions, customer business income and the development of MSMEs. (1) Providing smooth and well-targeted financing can increase customers' positive perceptions of BPRS. Customers will feel trusted and supported in developing their business, thereby strengthening the relationship between BPRS and customers. (2) Financing provided wisely and on target can help customers increase production capacity or expand their business. This has the potential to increase customers' business income and provide positive economic benefits for them. (3) BPRS as a sharia financing institution has an important role in supporting the development of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Appropriate financing can help MSMEs overcome liquidity constraints, expand their business, create jobs, and contribute to local economic growth.

Twentieth, profit sharing calculation system for Mudharabah financing products with moral hazard. Moral hazard refers to the risk that the capital manager (mudharib) may act irresponsibly because he does not bear the full loss. To overcome this, BPRS needs to implement a fair profit sharing calculation system and carefully consider risk factors in determining profit distribution.

Twenty-first, legal protection for creditors in private fiduciary agreements. A private fiduciary agreement is an agreement used by creditors (financing providers) and debtors (financing recipients) as a form of collateral

for the financing provided. In the context of BPRS, private fiduciary agreements must comply with sharia principles, and these banks are responsible for providing appropriate legal protection to creditors in terms of the transfer or implementation of fiduciary collateral in the event of default by the debtor.

Twenty-second, sharia compliance for Murabahah and Musyarakah financing. Murabahah is a sale and purchase agreement with disclosed (transparent) profits where the bank as the seller buys goods requested by the customer and sells them back to the customer with additional profits as a replacement for the bank for the financing provided. Meanwhile, Musyarakah is a cooperation agreement between the bank as the capital owner and the customer as the business owner in managing the business and sharing the profits according to the agreement. BPRS must ensure that the financing they provide based on these contracts is in accordance with sharia principles.

Twenty-third, application of Qardh and Murabahah contracts in the transfer of financing. A Qardh contract is a loan agreement with the requirement of returning the principal without additional profits. BPRS can use this contract in transferring financing, for example when switching financing from Murabahah contract-based financing to Qardh contract-based financing to help customers who experience payment difficulties to be more flexible in the payment process.

Twenty-third, resolution of financing conflicts/disputes. If there is a conflict or dispute related to financing between BPRS and customers, the resolution must comply with sharia principles. Usually, BPRS will try to reach a settlement through deliberation and mediation with customers to find an agreement that is fair and in accordance with Islamic law.

Twenty-fourth, application of the Buy Back Guarantee in the financing cooperation agreement. Buy Back Guarantee is a clause in a financing cooperation agreement that allows banks to buy back goods or assets that they have sold to customers, if the customer cannot fulfill their obligations in accordance with the agreement. In this way, the bank will take over the assets again and can look for other ways to complete the financing.

Twenty-fifth, financing credit restructuring during the Covid-19 pandemic. During the Covid-19 pandemic, many customers experienced difficulty in paying their financing credit due to the economic impact caused by the pandemic. In this situation, BPRS may consider restructuring credit financing for affected customers. Credit restructuring is changing existing financing terms to better suit the customer's financial situation, so that they can continue making payments more easily and easily.

Twenty-sixth, Murabahah financing insurance is based on Islamic law. Murabahah financing is a form of financing with a goods buying and selling scheme, where the bank buys goods desired by the customer and sells them back to the customer at a determined price and adds a pre-agreed profit margin. This insurance aims to provide protection against risks that may occur during the financing period.

Twenty-seventh, financing the Hajj bailout fund. Hajj bailout financing is a financing service offered by BPRS to prospective Hajj pilgrims who need financial assistance to perform the Hajj pilgrimage. This Hajj bailout fund allows prospective Hajj pilgrims to obtain financing with terms and conditions that apply in sharia principles, such as the absence of interest or usury in the financing.

Twenty-eighth, resolution of default cases in Murabahah financing. Default in Murabahah financing occurs when the customer fails to fulfill his

obligations in paying installments or paying off debts in accordance with the agreed agreement. Settlement of default cases in Murabahah financing must be carried out based on sharia principles, with efforts to find solutions that are fair and pro-both parties. Usually, resolution of default cases is carried out through deliberation between the bank and the customer to reach an agreement that allows the customer to pay off his obligations.

Twenty-ninth, the implications of personality, customer wa'd/ promise, amount of financing, customer income, repayment period in the financing refund commitment. In sharia financing, the implications of the customer's personality, wa'd/promise, amount of financing, customer's income, and repayment period are important factors that must be considered in the commitment to return financing funds. Personality implications relate to customer honesty and fairness in transactions and paying off their obligations. Wa'd or customer promise is the customer's commitment to comply with the agreements stipulated in the financing contract. The amount of financing and the customer's income are the bank's considerations in determining the customer's ability to pay installments. The repayment period must be adjusted to the customer's capabilities and not be burdensome in payments.

Thirtieth, analysis of non-Muslim customers' interest in sharia financing. Analysis of non-Muslim customers' interest in using sharia financing aims to understand the factors that influence non-Muslim customers' interest in using sharia financing products. Several factors that can influence this interest include understanding sharia principles, interest in products that are free from interest or usury, belief in justice and transparency in the sharia system, as well as the ethical and moral values that underlie sharia bank operations. This analysis is important for developing effective marketing strategies in attracting non-Muslim customers to use sharia financing services offered by BPRS.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Savings Products at Sharia Rural Financing Banks (BPRS)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 6 topics related to savings products at BPRS, namely:

First, deposit product management procedures. In the procedure for managing this deposit product, there are several stages that are generally followed: (1) Deposit Receipt: The customer deposits funds to the bank in the form of a deposit. These funds are considered a trust (wadiyah) managed by the bank. (2) Contract Agreement: The customer and the bank agree through a wadiyah yad dhamanah contract. This contract contains an agreement regarding the level of profit (nisbah) that will be given by the bank to the customer in return for the funds deposited. (3) Fund Management: The Bank will use funds collected from deposits to carry out financing based on the mudharabah principle (cooperation between fund owners and managers). (4) Profit Sharing: Profits from financing carried out by the bank will be shared between the bank and the customer based on the agreement in the contract. The bank will receive a fixed share (for example, 30%), while the remainder will be given to the customer according to the agreed ratio. (5) Reporting and Disbursement of Deposits: Banks are obliged to provide periodic reports regarding deposit activities. Customers can withdraw deposits at maturity or beforehand by fulfilling the agreed conditions.

Second, calculation of the profit sharing from Mudharabah savings. Profit sharing on mudharabah savings is calculated based on the ratio agreed between the bank and the customer in the contract. The amount of profit generated from

investment or financing using deposit funds is divided according to this ratio. For example, if the profit sharing ratio is 70:30 (70% for the customer and 30% for the bank) and the profit obtained from financing is IDR 10,000,000, then the customer will get $70\% \times \text{IDR } 10,000,000 = \text{IDR } 7,000,000$ and the bank will get $30\% \times \text{IDR } 10,000,000 = \text{IDR } 3,000,000$.

Third, analysis of intangible value for savings results. Intangible value in the context of mudharabah savings is related to the blessings and abundance that customers are believed to receive when investing their funds according to sharia. Even though this value is difficult to measure materially, many customers choose this product because of the belief that the profits they get will be more blessed and halal. Factors such as transparency in contracts, managing funds in accordance with sharia principles, and participation in social activities or poverty alleviation can also add intangible value for customers.

Fourth, wadiah yadh-dhamanah savings products, sacrificial savings, precious metal investment savings. (1) Wadiah Yad Dhamanah Savings: This product is a wadiah yad dhamanah contract-based savings, where customers entrust funds to the bank and the bank is responsible for safeguarding and managing these funds. Banks do not provide compensation (nisbah) for this type of savings. (2) Sacrifice Savings: This savings is specifically for saving funds that will be used for sacrifices on the Eid al-Adha holiday. The customer saves funds with the intention of sacrificing, and the bank is responsible for managing these funds according to sharia principles until they are needed to carry out the sacrifice. (3) Precious Metal Investment Savings: This type of savings provides customers with the option of saving in the form of precious metals such as gold or silver. Banks act as custodians of these precious metals and provide convenience in buying and selling transactions or disbursement.

Fifth, the influence of the profit sharing ratio, promotional costs, inflation on Mudharabah savings. (1) The higher the ratio for customers, the greater the potential profit that the customer can receive, but the bank will get a smaller share. On the other hand, if the ratio for the bank is higher, the bank's profits will be greater, but customers will get a smaller share of these profits. (2) If promotional costs are high, the profits obtained by the bank from managing customer funds may decrease. However, effective promotional costs can also increase the number of customers interested in opening mudharabah savings. (3) If the inflation rate is higher than the profits obtained, the real value of customer funds may decrease. To compensate for inflation, the profit sharing ratio must be set wisely so that customers continue to receive profits in line with economic growth or inflation.

Sixth, the influence of profit calculations, Quality of Productive Assets/KAP, Non-Performing Financing /NPF, financing, Return on Assets /ROA, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR on the profit sharing of Mudharabah savings.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues in Sharia Rural Financing Banks (BPRS)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 22 research topics related to BPRS issues, namely:

First, operational risk management and mitigation. BPRS must have a good operational risk management system to ensure efficiency and security in carrying out its operational activities. This involves the process of monitoring, controlling and implementing mitigation measures to reduce the possibility of risks and their impacts. Regular internal audits and monitoring are also

important in ensuring compliance with established policies and procedures to address operational risks.

Second, indications of financial inclusion in rural areas and the contribution of BPRS. BPRS plays an important role in increasing the level of financial inclusion in rural areas due to its sharia-based structure and focus on serving communities with broader financial needs. BPRS provides banking services that are more easily accessible to rural communities, including micro financing and productive credit programs for micro, small and medium enterprises in the region. With a sharia concept that prioritizes justice and shared prosperity, BPRS can also help reduce economic disparities in rural areas and encourage sustainable economic growth by providing access to financing for sectors that have economic potential in the region.

Third, money laundering and terrorism financing. BPRS, like other financial institutions, must be very careful in preventing money laundering and terrorism financing. Money laundering is the illegal practice of hiding the origin of money obtained from illegal activities or crimes to make it appear as if it came from a legitimate source. Meanwhile, terrorism financing is an effort to provide or collect funds with the aim of supporting acts of terrorism. BPRS must have strict systems and procedures to identify and report suspicious transactions to the competent authorities. This includes implementing strict "Know Your Customer" (KYC) policies, suspicious transaction reporting (STR), and cooperation with authorities in dealing with acts of money laundering and terrorism financing.

Fourth, it is against the law in the abuse of authority by the main director. Abuse of authority by the President Director or authorized parties at BPRS is an act against the law and ethics. Abuse of authority can include misuse of customer funds, manipulation of financial data, or other acts of corruption that harm the bank and its customers. To prevent and overcome abuse of authority, BPRS must have a strict and transparent monitoring system, including through regular internal and external audits. In addition, it is necessary to implement a code of ethics and training that ensures all employees, including the President Director, understand the legal and ethical consequences of abuse of authority. If there is a suspicion of abuse of authority, the BPRS must immediately involve the competent legal authorities to carry out appropriate investigations and legal action.

Fifth, allowance for uncollectible receivables on Qardh products. Uncollectible receivables are receivables that the borrower or customer will most likely not be able to pay. The Qardh product is a 0% interest-based financing product provided by BPRS to help customers with urgent needs or obtain interest-free financing. Allowance for bad debts on Qardh products is an accounting action to record potential losses that may arise because the receivables cannot be recovered. BPRS needs to carry out careful credit analysis before providing this type of financing to ensure the customer's ability to pay. However, sometimes, there is an unavoidable risk of default. By providing provisions for bad debts, BPRS can reflect more realistic financial conditions and deal with possible losses earlier, which in turn affects the bank's financial performance and stability.

Sixth, business planning. In this business planning, BPRS must also describe how they will market and promote their sharia products and services to the public. Financial plans are also an important part of business planning to describe the financial resources needed, projected income, and projected expenses to achieve predetermined business goals.

Seventh, an accounting information system for accounts receivable losses using the aging of receivables method and client server- based analysis of receivables turnover. The Loss Receivables Accounting Information System is a system used by Sharia Rural Banks (BPRS) to monitor, manage and assess the risk of receivables that may be uncollectible from customers. The aging of receivables method is used to classify receivables based on the age or length of time the receivables have not been paid. Usually, receivables are divided into several categories such as receivables that are still within the normal payment period, receivables that have passed the payment period, and receivables that are very past the payment deadline. Apart from that, receivables turnover analysis is also carried out to measure the efficiency of the receivables collection process by BPRS. By using a client-server based accounting information system, receivables data and related information can be accessed and managed more efficiently and accurately, enabling BPRS to make better decisions in managing receivables and minimizing the risk of loss.

Eighth, the role of BPRS in the community economy. Several important roles of BPRS in the community economy include: (1) Financial Inclusion: BPRS plays an important role in expanding financial access for people who have not been served by conventional financial institutions. By providing sharia-based financial services, BPRS provides opportunities for people who want to make transactions halally and in accordance with sharia principles. (2) Poverty Alleviation: BPRS also plays a role in alleviating poverty by providing financing for micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) which are the backbone of the community's economy. Support for MSMEs can increase people's income and welfare. (3) Provision of Sharia Financing: BPRS provides alternative sharia-based financing that is in accordance with the principles of justice and sustainability. This allows people to gain access to financing without involving usury elements. (4) Increasing Financial Education: BPRS has a role in increasing financial literacy and education for the community. By providing an understanding of sharia-based financial products and services, BPRS helps people make wise financial decisions.

Ninth, BPRS development strategies include: Human Resources (SDI) aspects, Service Aspects, Product Innovation Aspects, Networking Aspects, Regulatory Aspects, Public Education Aspects, Sharia Compliance Aspects, Synergy Aspects, Pro-Real Sector Aspects, Market Segmentation Aspects, Socio-Cultural Economic Interaction-Harmonization Aspects, and Media-Commodification Aspects.

Tenth, benefit index. The Benefits Index is a benchmark used by BPRS to measure their financial performance and success in achieving goals in accordance with sharia principles. This index covers aspects of financial performance, social performance and environmental performance. By using a benefit index, BPRS can measure the positive impact resulting from its business activities, rather than just focusing on achieving profits alone.

Eleventh, the role and responsibilities of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS regarding the implementation of Good Corporate Governance /GCG. The Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is the institution responsible for ensuring that BPRS carries out its operations in accordance with sharia principles and Good Corporate Governance (GCG) guidelines. DPS plays a role in providing advice and supervision over BPRS operational activities, thus ensuring that their activities do not violate sharia principles and avoid high potential risks.

Twelfth, company zakat. Corporate Zakat is an obligation for BPRS to pay zakat from the profits it obtains. Zakat is an important pillar in Islam, and in the corporate context, company zakat is calculated based on the income and profits earned, and there are special rules regarding company assets and debts. It is hoped that corporate zakat can help ease the burden on people in need and improve general welfare.

Thirteenth, comparison of revenue and profit sharing in the Mudharabah system. The Mudharabah system is one of the principles of financing in sharia economics where banks as capital owners (rab al-mal) provide funds to parties who wish to obtain financing (mudharib) for business. The profits generated from the business will be shared between the bank and the business party according to the initial agreement. The comparison of revenue and profit sharing in the Mudharabah system refers to the comparison of profit sharing between the bank as the capital owner and the business party.

Fourteenth, service quality with the Carter approach. Service Quality with the Carter approach is an approach to measuring and improving the quality of services provided by BPRS to customers. The Carter Approach is a method used to measure customer satisfaction by paying attention to aspects of service quality such as reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and the provision of additional services (responsiveness, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and reliability).

Fifteenth, the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR and zakat funds on community empowerment. In the context of BPRS, CSR can include various social programs and initiatives, such as education, health, environment and community economic empowerment. Zakat funds managed by BPRS can also be used to support CSR programs, so that people in need can be more empowered and benefit from the existence of BPRS. With CSR and well-managed zakat funds, BPRS can play a more active role in helping the community socially and economically.

Sixteenth, funding piggy bank. Piggy bank funding is a form of receiving funds from the public or customers which are saved in the form of piggy banks or savings. At BPRS, piggy bank funding is a very important source of funds to support operational activities and provide financing to customers. Funds from these piggy banks are usually managed according to sharia, so customers can be sure that their funds are used in accordance with Islamic sharia principles.

Seventeenth, the influence of financial risk and performance risk on customer switching barriers. These two types of risk can influence the level of customer satisfaction and trust in BPRS. If a BPRS experiences financial problems or poor performance, customers may be reluctant to switch to another BPRS for fear of facing the same or even worse risks. On the other hand, if a BPRS has good financial conditions and performance, customers will feel safer and more comfortable switching if deemed necessary. Therefore, risk management and good performance are very important in influencing customer loyalty.

Eighteenth, product marketing using the SWOT and AHP approaches. In product marketing, BPRS can use the SWOT approach to evaluate their position in the market and identify factors that influence product success. By understanding their strengths and weaknesses, SRBs can take action to improve the quality of products and services. In addition, through analyzing opportunities and threats in the market, BPRS can develop appropriate marketing strategies to increase market share and competitiveness. The AHP approach can also help BPRS in making decisions regarding product marketing.

By prioritizing various relevant criteria, such as customer needs, product excellence and market attractiveness, BPRS can determine the most effective and efficient marketing strategy.

Nineteenth, use of fintech. The use of fintech can help BPRS to become more competitive in the market, provide faster and more efficient services, and improve customer experience. However, it is important to remember that the use of fintech must also pay attention to the security and privacy aspects of customer data.

Twentieth, investment credit control through internal audit. In terms of investment credit control at BPRS, internal audit functions to ensure that policies and procedures related to providing financing or investment have been followed correctly and in accordance with sharia principles. Internal audit will identify potential problems or risks in the investment credit process, as well as provide recommendations for necessary improvements and preventative actions.

Twenty-first, implementation of DSN MUI fatwa no. 08 of 2000, no. 15 of 2000, no. 29 of 2002. The National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulama Council (DSN MUI) issued fatwas which became a reference for sharia banking practices in Indonesia. Fatwa No. 08 of 2000, no. 15 of 2000, and No. 29 of 2002 contains guidelines related to various aspects of BPRS operations, including management of funds, products and services, as well as operational procedures that must comply with sharia principles. BPRS are required to implement these fatwas in all their activities to ensure compliance with Islamic sharia principles and build customer trust.

Twenty-second, implementation of POJK No. 35 of 2018. In implementing POJK No. 35 of 2018 on Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), there are several things that must be considered and implemented by BPRS. Several key points in POJK No. 35 of 2018 which are relevant for BPRS include: (1) Risk Management: BPRS are required to have an adequate risk management system to identify, measure, control and monitor the risks faced in their operations. (2) Risk Assessment: BPRS must carry out regular risk assessments on all aspects of their operational activities, such as credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk, operational risk and other relevant risks. (3) Credit Risk Management: BPRS must have clear policies and procedures for managing credit risk, including assessing the creditworthiness of prospective debtors, monitoring credit quality periodically, and setting appropriate credit limits. (4) Liquidity Management: BPRS must maintain a balance between their assets and liabilities to ensure the availability of sufficient funds to meet customer financing needs and operational obligations. (5) Market Risk Management: BPRS that have open positions in the market (for example, due to fluctuations in interest rates or exchange rates) must have appropriate policies and strategies to manage market risk. (6) Compliance with Sharia Provisions: As sharia financial institutions, BPRS must also ensure that all their operational activities comply with the principles and provisions of Islamic sharia. (7) Transparency and Reporting: BPRS are required to report information about their risk management regularly to the OJK and other interested parties.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Islamic Rural Bankss (BPRS), namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee

performance; (3) Customer Behavior; (4) Financing products; (5) Savings products; and (6) Other issues.

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